

Tourism Infrastructure Development and Maintenance: The Instrumentality to Destination Competitiveness.

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Abstract:

The instrumentality of tourism infrastructure within tourism destination has been viewed by many scholars as being very critical (Adebayo and Iweka 2014). The infrastructure is as a result of development which the status quo is pointing to the local government as the leading partner in development followed by the local investors and then lastly the foreign investors. Continual usage will result in the dilapidation of these infrastructures, creating the need for continual and on-going maintenance mechanism to be strategized and to be put in place. Major challenges which are currently being faced by the developers included funding, easiness of doing business and poor stakeholder coordination. In conclusion, the empirical evidence reviewed the centrality of tourism infrastructure development and maintenance to tourism growth.

Key terms: *Tourism infrastructure, development, maintenance, and instrumentality.*

1.1 Introduction

Tourism is considered by many nations as the mainstay of economic development. The development of efficient infrastructural resources is key to modern tourism growth. Panasiuk (2017) identified 6 elements which were classified as tourism infrastructure, these included accommodation facilities, gastronomy facilities, transport facilities, range of activities, retail network and information communication technology. Tourism infrastructure like transport network systems acts as a bridge between places of tourist origin and destination. It opens out regions by providing access to its tourist places. In its absence, the potential for tourism within that region cannot be of any benefit. The availability of tourism infrastructure within a destination will determine the amount and structure of tourist movement within the destination.

In Zimbabwe tourism is ranked third after agriculture and mining. Therefore for the industry to continue generating revenue for the nation, there is a need for efficient and effective tourism infrastructure in place. In the year 2016, Zimbabwe received a total of 2167686 tourist arrivals, (ZTA 2017). This figure marked a 5% increase from 2015 total arrivals. This study, therefore, would want to assess the contribution of tourist infrastructure development and maintenance to tourism growth.

1.2 Background information.

The development of tourism infrastructure is the mandate of agents of development which include amongst themselves the public sector, the private sector, and the foreign investors. It is the mandate of the public sector through the government to take the lead in the development of basic infrastructure within tourism destinations to create a beneficial investment atmosphere for the private and the foreign investors. Due to infrastructural developmental challenges, strategies are being developed to enhance infrastructure development within tourism destinations. Amongst the strategies are the public-private partnerships (PPPs) where the government would allow the private sector to take the lead in the development in an agreed partnership looking at how the private sector will recoup its resources later on.

In tourism infrastructure development, it is very necessary to understand the sources of financing. They are different sources of finance which most government uses amongst them it included equity capital, credits, government grants and subsidies, EU funds. The commercial entities and the public entities have the possibility of taking up joint ventures through public-private partnership to develop both commercial infrastructure and public infrastructure which will subsequently benefit both the tourist and the general public.

1.2.1 Agents of development

1. The public sector. The public sector is steered by the government. The public sector provide commercial infrastructure these included roads, ports (airports, and seaports). The public sector infrastructure plays a role of providing access to private sector's tourism infrastructure for example accommodation facilities and facilitates to operationalize carrier infrastructure like aeroplanes and cruise ships. The public sector infrastructure can be used by both the tourist and the country's residence.

2. Private sector. The public sector is controlled by the investors within a specific industry. In the tourism industry the private constitutes the operators. They are termed private entities and their concern is on return on investment as a result they invest where there is money in return. The development in the private sector is concentrated on accommodation facilities, transport facilities, information technology facilities and attraction maintenance and development. Other amenities like hospitals, postal services and banks do not constitute much on tourism infrastructure development.

3. Foreign Investors. Investment is an essential component of the more competitive and faster development of tourism infrastructure. Destinations are very dynamic and relying on direct or indirect investors. Investments in the tourism industry can be generated by the state, private and the foreign investors who will be willing to take part in tourism destination development.

2.1 Tourism infrastructure development challenges

Due to its contribution through a wider supply chain system, tourism infrastructure development is characterised by a number of challenges which included:

2.1.1 Tourism as a secondary user- at national level, tourism is normally not given due diligence, resulting in it being placed as a secondary industry when investments priorities are agreed upon at national level. Key tourism infrastructure like roads and airports plays a secondary fable during national planning and policy formulation strategic meetings.

2.1.2 Planning, Approval and regulatory barriers- State and local statutory planning instruments can prevent tourism infrastructure development. There are many licences which are usually required prior to the development and this will result in delays or stopping investors from investing.

2.1.3 Lack of certainty of tourism marketing funding- due to the fact that most of tourism infrastructure is developed by the private sector, the private sector is unlikely to invest in significant demand-driving infrastructure or supporting visitor infrastructure if there is uncertainty around tourism marketing funding for a particular destination.

2.1.4 Untargeted government funding- due to the fact that tourism is considered in the local mainstream development projects, in some cases funds are usually mismanaged by the local authority resulting in disadvantaging the tourism sector.

3.1 Maintenance mechanism for tourism infrastructure.

Maintenance is defined as work undertaken to keep or restore every facility in the property to an acceptable standard. Lind and Muyingo (2009), further define maintenance as all technical and administrative actions undertaken to maintain or restore the functionality of an item. As a result, maintenance can be considered as action taken by any authority to restore or maintain the conditions of an item so that it performs a specific function as intended by the maintenance process.

The fact that tourism is considered by many governments as the major contributor to nation's development, it needs to be always supported through the proper management and maintenance of its infrastructure. The government of Malaysia has since discovered this, and it is always at the forefront in investing heavily towards the provision of sufficient and well-functioning public tourism infrastructure.

The development and maintenance of infrastructure are interlinked. They both impact on the growth of any tourism industry. There is need to provide related infrastructure and maintain it to preserve the functionality

of it. If infrastructure within a destination is poor, it will lead to premature damage, unsafe usage and problems with the functionality of the infrastructure. The end result will be a dissatisfied with tourist and consequently uncompetitive destination. The development of infrastructure must be accompanied by maintenance activities to avoid obsolescence and damage. On-going neglect of maintenance activities will lead to severe damage to infrastructure.

3.1.1 Challenges associated with tourism infrastructure maintenance

They are major challenges associated with the execution of maintenance work, and these are below:

- **Resources:** The resources which are required include finance, personnel, equipment, and materials.
- **Lack of effective maintenance management system:** For the proper execution of maintenance work, there is a need for teamwork. It requires all managerial aspects including planning, organizing, implementation, and control to be in-play. Management must know when to carry out maintenance work. Management systems also include aspects of doing with guidelines. If there is lack of guidelines, it means it will be difficult to execute any maintenance work.
- **Lack of policies and specific maintenance strategies:** There is a need for a clear and defined maintenance policy. A policy is a document which can be used as a source of reference. It is there to explain the framework of maintenance, the methods of operational management, the availability of funding for maintenance purposes and the level of priority for all maintenance activities. So, if all this is not spelled out clearly, it means maintenance work is being done at *ad hoc* bases. There is also need for a maintenance strategy which is defined as a means to achieve an end. So the strategies in maintenance work are the tactics which are going to be used to achieve proper maintenance output.
- **Lack of maintenance culture:** There is need to train people on the importance of effective infrastructure within the tourism industry. Operators and travelers need to be trained to be responsible in the way they use the infrastructure within a destination.

Infrastructure maintenance is market driven. Most companies engage in infrastructural maintenance so as to keep pace with the changes and requirements of the target market.

4.1 Strategies for the enhancement of tourism infrastructure development

A strategy can be defined as a means to achieve a goal. For the enhancement and development of tourism infrastructure destinations need to have strategies for effectiveness. The strategies need to be implemented and monitored. Many countries realize the potential tourism has for the development of national economy. As a result government and private operators are putting strategies together to harness the tourism benefits effectively.

Good tourism infrastructure results in many tourists visiting the country. This was supported by Jovanovic (2016) when he said infrastructure is important for economic growth and its one of the main factor of the failure to attract foreign investors. He further on said the provision of infrastructure is one of the key factors that contribute to the increasing number of tourist. As a result, some strategies were noticed and evaluated to have an effect on the enhancement of tourism infrastructure development. Below is a list of strategies which some government used:

- The destination region must be developed as an industrial zone
- Creation of an environment conducive for tourism infrastructure development.
- The policy framework to support investors. The following policies were revised in some countries:
 - Tax regime
 - License acquiring procedures
 - Regulatory environment and the creation of a single authority for tourism promotion
 - Investment approval in line with the creation of “one-stop shop” for tourism related investments
 - Provision of land for tourism related infrastructure development

- Incorporating small to medium enterprises (SMEs) in tourism infrastructure development
- The development of public-private partnerships. The government must work together with the private sector to develop tourism infrastructure

It must be noted that good infrastructure is a result of government commitment towards infrastructure development. More resources must be allocated towards tourism infrastructure development.

5.1 Empirical evidence on the instrumentality of tourism development and maintenance to tourism growth

Data for this research was collected from two prime destinations in Zimbabwe (Victoria Falls and Nyanga), and the analysis was made using a 5-point Likert scale, and the summary statistics are presented in Table 1.1 below.

Table 1.1 Ideal Infrastructural Development and Maintenance Responsibilities Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean		Std. Deviation	Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
Government	540	4.70	.033	.775	9.843	.210
Foreign investors	543	4.71	.030	.704	12.289	.209
Local Private companies	537	4.74	.028	.653	16.464	.210
Valid N (listwise)	537					

The results above displays a significant difference from the status quo as presented in literature where the government takes the leading role in infrastructure development and maintenance. However, the results reviewed having the government’s role being rather lower than the present, as seen with the least mean rating of 4.70. The highest rating was observed with the local investors, and these had the highest mean rating of 4.74, while foreign investors were rated second, with a mean of 4.71.

With a view to evaluating whether these ideal responsibilities are the same as the status quo or different, according to Field (2016), the paired t-test analysis would be optimal. This was carried out, and the results are summarized in Table 1.2 below.

Table 1.1 : Paired Samples Test – Current vs. Ideal Stakeholder Responsibilities Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Government	.034	.821	.036	-.036	.104	.949	533	.343
Pair 2	Foreign investors	-.212	.866	.037	-.286	-.139	-5.682	536	.000
Pair 3	Local investors	-.107	.793	.034	-.175	-.040	-3.121	530	.002

From the foregoing, therefore in respect to the government, $t(533) = 0.949$; $p > 0.05$. Effectively, it follows that there was not enough statistical evidence that the proposed extent of government was different from the status quo. In other words, from a broader perspective, the respondents tended to insinuate that the current level of engagement of the government was adequate.

Nevertheless, from the results, the gap between the current and the ideal level of engagement of local and foreign investors was very significant. For foreign investors, $t(533) = -5.682$; $p < 0.05$. For local investors, $t(533) = -3.121$; $p < 0.05$. The negative t-statistic shows that there was a significant deficit from the ideal level of involvement suggesting that that the level of engagement of local and foreign stakeholders ought to be stepped up. The latter can be substantiated by the significant difference that was observed with respect to the current and perceived ideal level of engagement of both local and foreign investors. In a nutshell, with a view to improving the tourism infrastructure, the respondents concurred that more efforts were supposed to be leveraged from the investors.

5.1.1 Current Motives behind Tourism Infrastructure Development and Maintenance

The three agents for development were assessed their motives of involvement in tourism infrastructure development and the tables below summaries the results.

Table 1.2 Motives of the Government behind Infrastructure Development/Maintenance Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean		Std. Deviation	Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
National duty	540	4.60	.035	.815	6.868	.210
Provision of leisure facilities to its communities	540	4.67	.028	.649	5.221	.210
Improving country’s image	543	4.70	.028	.658	12.046	.209
As a tool for economic growth	543	4.78	.023	.529	17.469	.209
Valid N (listwise)	537					

Table 1.3: Motives of the Investors behind Infrastructure Development/Maintenance Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean		Std. Deviation	Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
Profit generation	540	4.77	.025	.579	12.908	.210
Diversification of organizational product	537	4.69	.027	.635	5.031	.210
Increase market share	537	4.75	.023	.538	5.312	.210
Achievement on rate of return on investment	537	4.77	.021	.494	6.499	.210
Valid N (listwise)	534					

Qualitative analysis was carried out to get a deeper understanding of the motives of development. Seven tourism related institutions were interviewed, and the summary of the findings is presented in table 1.5 below.

Table 1.4: Institutional motives for tourism infrastructure development.

Institution	Motive for development
Civil Aviation Authority of Zimbabwe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wealth creation for the government • Profit generation for the private sector
Hospitality association	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of an enabling environment

of Zimbabwe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Banks – provision of loans to the developers
Ministry of transport and infrastructural development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate the traveling of long-haul travelers • Revenue generation • Creation of destination visibility
Ministry of Tourism and Hospitality Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revenue creation • Association • Provision of basic necessities to the local residences • Safeguarding territorial environment • As a national duty
Zimbabwe council for Tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market driven • Government as a salient partner • Generation of revenue
Zimbabwe Parks and Wildlife management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional mandate • Creation and maintenance of image and visibility
Zimbabwe Tourism Authority	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of wealth • Visibility • Institutional protection

The seven selected tourism related institutions concurred on a holistic approach to destination infrastructural development, with all stakeholders participating for a destination to be competitive. The notion of all stakeholder involvement was viewed as a noble idea by all the seven institutions. Three motives from the summary stand out to be the most important motives for development and this included revenue generation, profit maximization and visibility.

With the aim of keeping the infrastructure to an acceptable standard, maintenance work needs to be done regularly. The seven institutions agreed on the following sector to take the lead in infrastructural maintenance and these included:

- Ministry of Tourism and Hospitality Industry;
- Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure Development;
- The private sector operators;
- Local authorities; and
- Development partners.

Asked on who should fund the maintenance work, the interviewee identified the following stakeholders:

- Ministry of Finance and Economic Development;
- The private sector operators; and
- Foreign investors.

The government through ZTA must enforce regulations on tourism infrastructure maintenance through operational standards.

5.1.2 Summary on challenges facing agents for development in infrastructural development and maintenance mechanisms

Figure 1.1

6.1 Discussion of Findings

In terms of the current responsibilities, the Government was wedging the greatest responsibility for tourism infrastructure development and maintenance, followed by local investors while the foreign investors had the least responsibility. The status quo is supported by the literature with scholars such as Benedetti (2010) and Inskip (1991), reinforcing those local authorities *cum* government ought to take the lead in the development of tourism infrastructure. It is noted further that the fact that while the private sector is profit-oriented, public amenities may not fall within their purview, as some of the infrastructures do not immediately generate profits, neither may they be meant for generating profit, being basic amenities, such as roads, water, electricity, health services and inter alia, public transportation (Seetanah, 2011).

From the findings, the research further confirmed that the levels of involvement of the different stakeholders differed significantly, depending on the tourist site. The Government as well as foreign investors seemed to be biased towards the major tourist site, Victoria Falls. While it may be rational to prioritise state resources towards the most productive tourist destinations, the key role of the Government is mainly as a result of their national duty obligation (Abdullah, 2014), mainly as a result of the understanding that it will as well benefit indirectly from the revenue inflows trickling as a result of the viability of the tourism sector performance. In this respect, careful consideration ought to be made to ensure adequate resuscitation and maintenance of other tourist destinations as well.

7.1 Conclusion

The role of tourism infrastructural development and maintenance was viewed as being very critical to destination development and tourism growth. The research reviewed the importance of all stakeholder involvement in tourism development and maintenance with the government taking the leading. The gap between the current activities by the local and foreign investors and the expected level of engagement was established to be statistically significant. It is in this respect that the researcher concludes that there tends to be structural deficiencies in the multilateral engagements that ought to be in place to ensure the collective engagement by the government and tourism industry towards tourism infrastructural development and maintenance. In other words, the researcher concludes that the current culture points to the fact that tourism players expect much of the development and maintenances as being the primary mandate of the government overshadowing the need for the multilateral collective engagement between all the involved stakeholders (Swarbrooke, 2002; Franco, 2010; Abdullah, 2014; and Medhekar, 2014)

For successful tourism growth, there is need for more intensive investments in the development and maintenance of tourism infrastructure. The achievements of high level of tourism infrastructure contribute immensely to increased efficiency of production and distribution of tourism resources.

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